

EFFICIENCY OF USING SCAMPER TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING PROCESS

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Annotation. This article deals with the importance of SCAMPER technology in education and how it can be used more effectively in learning process.

Keywords: SCAMPER strategy, Classroom action research, motivation

The SCAMPER is an innovative technique that can be implemented in learning process broadly and effectively. These technique is helpful in creating highly motivated classroom environment and increase learning efficiency among students. SCAMPER derived from a brainstorming technique initially proposed by Osborne (1993) which was further developed and introduced to education by Eberle (1997). SCAMPER is an acronym that combines seven words: S for Substitute, C for Combine, A for Adapt, M for Magnify, P for Put to other use, E for Eliminate, and R for Reverse. This technique can help teachers to incorporate more classroom activities and creative, practical lessons, so that students find it easier to comprehend the concepts better.

Substitute - replacing it with something else, analyzing, observing the results. Testing with an alternative always helps you to understand which one works better for you.

Combine - Sometimes, combining two different kinds of teaching processes might turn out to be a great idea generating better processes results. Or combining different ideas and knowledge during the brainstorming can give better understanding.

Adapt -Adapting from surroundings and the environment helps to develop solutions way earlier and quickly. For instance, adapting different types of games from the environment will help students relate to lessons in a far better manner. It demands from student to think deeply and critically.

Modify/Magnify -modify or add or remove any aspect in the teaching process to give you a new perspective that will help you look at things differently. It is also names ad magnify or minify.

Put to use - putting into practice what has been learned.

SCAMPER strategy develops learners' thinking , encourages them to enrich their ideas and improve them to discover new alternatives to solve problems. In addition to, SCAMPER strategy works to support and strengthen the levels of creativity for students when dealing with difficulties and thinking of solutions.

Eberel (2008,p. 8) demonstrated many characteristics of SCAMPER strategy as follow:

- 1- Activating the role of the student in educational situations.
- 2- Motivating students to generate ideas about any topic.
- 3- Developing thinking skills in general and productive thinking in particular for learners.
- 4- Stimulating curiosity and taking risks.
- 5- Developing the student's skill in raising different motivational questions.
- 6- Developing imagination, especially the creative imagination for learners.
- 7- Creating positive attitudes among learners towards learning subject matter, thinking, imagination and innovation

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